

Evolution of Reduced Competitive Ability (ERCA) hypothesis on islands: low competitor pressure drives evolution of decreased growth, increased reproduction and herbivore tolerance in nonnative plants

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Introduction

The Evolution of Reduced Competitive Ability (ERCA) hypothesis posits that nonnative plant populations invading habitats with low competitive pressure (few competing species or individuals per unit area) will rapidly evolve decreased vegetative growth in favor of other traits such as reproductive effort and herbivore tolerance. The ERCA hypothesis addresses recent calls for an expanded consideration of habitat characteristics that might drive post-establishment evolution. We provide the first test of the ERCA hypothesis by growing nonnative plant populations from high and low competitive environments in a two-year common garden.

We previously demonstrated that habitats on nearshore islands along the New England coast host fewer competing species and individuals per unit area than nearby mainland habitats. We further showed that, in some cases, the ERCA hypothesis accurately described the way in which nonnative plants responded to the removal of their competing neighbors: relative to individuals in high competitive environments, individuals in low competitive environments experienced a lesser increase in vegetative growth but a greater increase in reproductive effort, as well as reduced herbivore damage. However, no single species utilized in our neighbor removal study demonstrated all three predicted responses in growth, reproduction, and herbivore tolerance (Atwood and Meyerson 2010a).

To further test the ERCA hypothesis, we utilized a common garden in which we germinated nonnative seeds collected from high and low competitive environments, represented respectively by mainland and nearshore island habitats along the New England coastline, including several populations from Nantucket. We utilized three nonnative plant species commonly found in New England: *Lythrum salicaria* (purple loosestrife), *Solanum dulcamara* (bittersweet nightshade) and *Vincetoxicum nigrum* (black swallow wort). We asked whether mainland and island populations would differ in growth, reproduction, and/or herbivore tolerance when grown under identical conditions for two growing seasons. Because the presence or absence of competition has in some cases been shown to change the outcome of common garden experiments (Leger and Rice 2003; Blumenthal and Hufbauer 2007), we repeated our study for three separate growth scenarios: plants were grown alone, with one competing individual of the native plant *Solidago canadensis*, or with two competing *S. canadensis* individuals. We predicted that island populations would produce less biomass and more fruit mass per unit biomass than mainland populations in each of our three growth scenarios. We further asked whether mainland and island populations would differ in their response to simulated herbivory and predicted that leaf damage would have a lesser effect on biomass production in island populations than in mainland populations (Agrawal et al. 2005; Rogers and Siemann 2005). Our collective results provide a description of rapid evolution for specific traits related to survival and fecundity in nonnative plants.

We also examined genetic variability in our three study species in order to evaluate total molecular variation in our populations. We used an Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP) analysis to partition genetic variability among geographic groups, among populations within groups, and within populations. We asked whether individuals within populations were more similar to one another than they were to individuals of other populations, which might suggest local adaptation within populations.

Methods and Materials

We chose three study species to test our hypotheses across multiple plant families: *L. salicaria* (Lythraceae), *S. dulcamara* (Solanaceae), and *Vincetoxicum nigrum* (Apocynaceae). We used herbaceous perennials because these species have shorter generation times, providing more opportunities for genetic recombination following introduction than would long-lived woody species. We selected species that are commonly found along the New England coast and were introduced from Western Europe to North America in the early-to-mid 1800s (Crossley 1974; Stuckey 1980; DiTommaso et al. 2005). All three species reproduce primarily by seed, providing opportunities for genetic recombination (Thompson et al. 1987; Francis 2004; DiTommaso et al. 2005).

Sites utilized for seed collection (Fig. 1) were selected at random from a database of known sites based on personal observations and records from the Invasive Plant Atlas of New England (IPANE). Sites were separated by a minimum distance of 1 km (Jakobs et al. 2004; Handley et al. 2008). At each site, fruits were collected from ten individuals selected at random using a random numbers table. Individuals were at least 3 m from one another. *S. dulcamara* fruits were macerated and seeds were cleaned and dried; dry seeds were collected directly from ripe fruits of *L. salicaria* and *V. nigrum*. Seeds were homogenized by population and stored from November 2008 to March 2009 at 4°C. *S. canadensis* seeds were obtained commercially in February 2009. *V. nigrum* seeds were wet stratified for one month prior to germination. Seeds were planted in moistened SunGro Metro Mix 510 potting soil in a greenhouse in March 2009. After six weeks seedlings were transplanted into pots and moved outdoors. For each population, 10 individuals were planted alone in one-gallon pots, 10 individuals were planted in two-gallon pots with a single *S. canadensis* competitor, and 10 individuals were planted in three-gallon pots with two *S. canadensis* competitors. We kept the ratio of soil space to individuals constant to avoid confounding density with competition (Gurevitch et al. 1990; Snaydon 1991; Gibson et al. 1999). We chose *S. canadensis* as a competitor because it is native to North America, commonly found at our seed collection sites, and is an aggressive invader outside of its native range (Wu et al. 2004). An additional 10 individuals were planted alone in one-gallon pots for use in our simulated herbivory treatment, in which a hole-punch was used to perforate each leaf with a single hole along the midvein approximately $\frac{1}{4}$ of the leaf's length from the petiole. This treatment was repeated monthly from June to September in 2009 and May to September in 2010. Initial biomass measurements were taken in June 2009 using the following allometric equations, where x is total stem length and y is biomass: for *L. salicaria* $y=0.1089x+4.2821$, for *S. dulcamara* $y=0.0773x+7.0382$, for *V. nigrum* $y=0.037x+4.915$, for *S. canadensis* $y=0.1158x+19.191$.

Between June 1 and August 15 in both 2009 and 2010, all individuals received biweekly foliar applications of 2.5% Permethrin (Eight Insect Control) diluted at 30 ml/gal at a rate of 1 gal diluted mixture per 800 pots. Lepidopteran larvae, chrysomelid beetles, and aphids were observed in low numbers in early June but were effectively managed by pesticide applications. Pots were overwintered between late November 2009 and early April 2010 in a greenhouse with air temperatures fluctuating between 4°C and 10°C. Individuals were watered as needed to avoid desiccation. Flowering phenology (the number of days from germination to flowering) was recorded twice weekly from June to September 2010. We calculated the competitive response of *S. canadensis* individuals as the ratio of total stem length of an individual grown in competition to the average total stem length of 20 *S. canadensis* individuals grown alone (Goldberg and Fleetwood 1987; Weigelt and Jolliffe 2003). In early September 2010 all fruits and aboveground biomass were collected. Roots were gently washed and manually separated. All samples were oven-dried to constant mass at 46°C before weighing. Reproductive mass ratio ReMR was calculated as (fruit mass)/(total biomass). ReMR data were log normalized to meet assumptions of normality; all other data were normally distributed. We performed a nested

ANOVA with population nested inside origin (mainland vs. island). Data from our herbivory experiment were analyzed using the interaction term origin*treatment.

AFLP analysis

We collected 50 mg of fresh leaf tissue from five individuals of each population within six weeks of germination and immediately froze all samples. We extracted genomic DNA using Qiagen DNeasy 96 kits per manufacturer protocols and used a Qiagen TissueLyser II to grind tissue samples. DNA was ethanol precipitated using 3M NaOAc (pH 5.2) and 95% EtOH and then resuspended in 5 μ L TE Buffer (pH 8.0) and stored at -20°C. We used Applied Biosystems (AB) Ligation and Preselective Amplification kits and restricted genomic DNA with EcoRI and MseI enzymes (New England Biolabs) per manufacturers' protocols. Selective amplification was conducted using the AB AFLP Plant Mapping Protocol (Applied Biosystems 2007) and utilized the selective primer combination MseI+CAA paired with EcoRI+AGC, which was fluorescently tagged with NED dye (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA). Amplification products were ethanol precipitated and then electrophoresed using an AB 3130xl Genetic Analyzer. Data were scored using GeneMapper v. 4.0 (Applied Biosystems 2005).

We used PAUP* 4.0 (Swofford 1998) to determine relationships among individuals and populations using a neighbor-joining distance analysis. We used the distance index of Nei and Li (1979) to estimate similarity and arbitrarily chose outgroups for each species ("Charlestown, RI 1" for *L. salicaria*, "Block Island, RI 4" for *S. dulcamara*, and "North Monhegan, ME 3" for *V. nigrum*). We calculated bootstrap values for neighbor-joining trees using 1000 replicate searches (Felsenstein 1985). We then used Arlequin v. 3.5.1.2 (Excoffier and Lischer 2010) to conduct analyses of molecular variance (AMOVA) to partition total molecular variance among groups of populations, among populations within groups, and within populations. We based our definition of groups on the phylogenies generated by our neighbor-joining analysis. We also used Arlequin to calculate fixation indices, F_{ST} , for each species.

Results

Common garden

Relative to mainland individuals, island individuals grown alone produced less belowground biomass ($P > 0.0001$ for each species) and less aboveground biomass ($P > 0.0001$ for each species). The change in total biomass over the 15-month growing period was lower in island individuals than in mainland individuals ($P > 0.0001$ for each species; Fig. 2).

Similar results were found when individuals were grown with a single *S. canadensis* competitor: island individuals, relative to mainland individuals, produced less belowground biomass ($P > 0.0001$ for each species), less aboveground biomass ($P > 0.0001$ for each species), and a lesser change in total biomass over the duration of the experiment ($P > 0.0001$ for each species, Fig 2).

When two *S. canadensis* competitors were present, belowground biomass was lower in island individuals of *L. salicaria* and *S. dulcamara* ($P > 0.0001$ for each species), but not in *V. nigrum* ($P = 0.6412$). Aboveground biomass was significantly lower in island populations of all three species ($P > 0.0001$ for each species), and the change in total biomass was lower in island populations of *L. salicaria* and *S. dulcamara* ($P > 0.0001$ for each species), but not *V. nigrum* ($P = 0.3505$; Fig 2).

The reproductive mass ratio (ReMR) was higher in island individuals than in mainland individuals when grown alone ($P > 0.0001$ for each species, Fig. 3), when individuals were grown with a single *S. canadensis* competitor ($P = 0.0004$ for *L. salicaria*, < 0.0001 for *S. dulcamara*, < 0.0001 for *V. nigrum*, Fig. 3), and when individuals were grown with two *S. canadensis* competitors ($P = 0.002$ for *L. salicaria*, < 0.0001 for *S. dulcamara*, 0.0218 for *V. nigrum*, Fig. 3).

Island individuals, relative to mainland individuals, in our herbivory treatment demonstrated a lesser decrease in their production of belowground biomass ($P > 0.0001$ for each

species), aboveground biomass ($P > 0.0001$ for each species), and in their change in total biomass ($P > 0.0001$ for each species, total biomass depicted in Fig 4).

When a single *S. canadensis* individual was grown with a target individual, the competitive response in *S. canadensis* was greater when competing with an island individual than when competing with a mainland individual for *V. nigrum* ($P < 0.0001$), but not for *L. salicaria* ($P = 0.4909$) or *S. dulcamara* ($P = 0.1047$, Fig. 5a). When two *S. canadensis* individuals were grown with a target individual, competitive response did not differ based on whether they were growing with an island or mainland individual ($P = 0.964$ for *L. salicaria*, 0.1718 for *S. dulcamara*, 0.1072 for *V. nigrum*, Fig. 5b).

Origin of population (mainland vs. island) did not affect the number of days to flower in any of our study species ($P = 0.1504$ for *L. salicaria*, 0.2647 for *S. dulcamara*, 0.1959 for *V. nigrum*). The difference in number of days to flower was also not significant between those *S. canadensis* individuals competing with mainland individuals and those competing with island individuals ($P = 0.2969$ for *L. salicaria*, 0.4374 for *S. dulcamara*, 0.5723 for *V. nigrum*).

AFLP analysis

Our amplification of restricted DNA fragments revealed a total of 119 polymorphic loci in *L. salicaria*, 92 in *S. dulcamara*, and 178 in *V. nigrum*. We analyzed data from each species separately and found that individual samples tended to cluster within populations, and that populations tended to cluster within geographic sampling regions, for each species (App. 1). We therefore grouped samples by geographic location (state of origin and mainland/island status) for the purposes of our analyses of molecular variance. Thus, our analysis included six groups: Maine mainland populations, Maine island populations, Massachusetts mainland populations, Massachusetts island populations, Rhode Island mainland populations, and Rhode Island island populations.

For *L. salicaria*, 15.85% of the total molecular variation was partitioned among groups, 37.55% was partitioned among populations within groups, and 46.60% was partitioned within populations. For *S. dulcamara*, 27.16% of total molecular variation was partitioned among groups, 12.63% was partitioned among populations within groups, and 60.21% was partitioned within populations. For *V. nigrum*, 20.54% of total molecular variation was partitioned among groups, 35.57% was partitioned among populations within groups, and 43.89% was partitioned within populations. The fixation index, F_{ST} , was 0.53 for *L. salicaria*, 0.40 for *S. dulcamara*, and 0.56 for *V. nigrum*. For comparison, we conducted additional AMOVA tests in which we grouped by state alone, in order to better understand the relationship between mainland and island populations (Table 1).

Discussion

Our data suggest that the ERCA hypothesis holds for *L. salicaria*, *S. dulcamara*, and *V. nigrum*. After demonstrating that nearshore islands in New England hosted fewer competing species and individuals per unit area than nearby coastal mainland habitats (Atwood and Meyerson 2010a), our data show that individuals from low competitive environments have rapidly evolved decreased vegetative growth (Fig. 2), increased reproductive effort (Fig. 3), and increased tolerance to herbivory (Fig. 4) relative to individuals from high competitive environments. While previous studies have shown that the presence or absence of competition can change the outcome of common garden experiments (Leger and Rice 2003; Blumenthal and Hufbauer 2007), our results indicate that the ERCA hypothesis holds for all three of our study species along a spectrum of competitive stress.

While competing *S. canadensis* individuals were generally larger when growing against island individuals (suggesting that island individuals are less competitive than mainland individuals), the difference in competitive response between *S. canadensis* individuals growing against island or mainland target individuals was only significant in one instance: when a single

S. canadensis competitor was grown with a single *V. nigrum* individual (Fig. 5). The use of the term “competitive ability” in the language of the ERCA hypothesis (and the earlier EICA hypothesis) may therefore be a misnomer: while we found the predicted evolved changes in growth, reproductive, and tolerance traits, the ability of individuals to competitively inhibit the growth of neighbors was less clearly demonstrated. The focus of research in post-establishment evolution should perhaps be shifted from “competitive ability” to more generally refer to evolved changes in traits related to survival and fecundity.

Our genetic analyses found that some of the total molecular variation in each species was partitioned among groups of populations based on geographic origin and island/mainland status, and among populations within groups (Table 1). Based on neighbor-joining, individuals of each species tended to cluster into populations based on geographic sampling location (App. 1), suggesting that some local adaptation has taken place for populations of *L. salicaria*, *S. dulcamara*, and *V. nigrum* along the New England coast. This provides support for the population-level adaptations in growth, reproductive, and tolerance traits recorded in the common garden, though the variability demonstrated by our AFLP analyses describes the entire genome and does not reflect variability in those specific traits (Hufbauer 2004). Population clustering was more apparent in *L. salicaria* and *V. nigrum* than in *S. dulcamara*, suggesting that geographically disparate populations of *S. dulcamara* may experience more interbreeding than do populations of *L. salicaria* or *V. nigrum*. This may be related to the mechanism of seed dispersal, as *S. dulcamara* is primarily dispersed by birds, whereas *L. salicaria* and *V. nigrum* seeds are primarily dispersed by wind (Rawinski 1982; Francis 2004; DiTommaso et al. 2005).

To date much of the research regarding post-establishment evolution in plants has focused on testing the EICA hypothesis and its suggestion that the lack of specialized herbivory in the invaded range acts as a selection pressure. Our data suggest that alternative selection pressures, such as the amount of competition in invaded habitats, also warrant examination. As any number of environmental variables in the invaded range could potentially act as selection pressures, we recommend a broader examination of post-establishment evolution rather than a continued focus on testing the EICA hypothesis (Callaway and Maron 2006; Whitney and Gabler 2008; Atwood and Meyerson 2010b).

While the ERCA hypothesis may be generally applicable to high and low competitive environments across mainland landscapes, we believe that it has particular significance for island habitats and island biogeography theory. Because islands, both oceanic and nearshore, tend to host fewer species and fewer individuals per unit area than mainland habitats (MacArthur and Wilson 1967; Sax et al. 2002; Atwood and Meyerson 2010a), we predict that nonnative plant populations invading islands from mainland habitats are more likely than mainland-to-mainland invasions to undergo the rapid evolutionary changes described by the ERCA hypothesis. We recommend future research that explores the implications of the ERCA hypothesis for invasions on both nearshore and oceanic islands.

Conclusion

Our results provide the first clear evidence for the ERCA hypothesis as an accurate predictor of post-establishment evolution. Our common garden analysis shows that populations originating from areas associated with low competitor richness and density (nearshore islands) demonstrate decreased vegetative growth, increased reproductive effort, and increased tolerance to herbivory relative to populations originating from areas associated with higher competitor richness and density. We were able to detect these trends along a spectrum of competitive scenarios in our common garden manipulations for each of our study species. We further demonstrated that some of the total molecular variation in *L. salicaria*, *S. dulcamara* and *V. nigrum* is partitioned among geographic groups and among populations. We found that individuals tend to cluster into populations based on geographic sampling locations, suggesting

the potential for local adaptations. Together our results strongly suggest that populations along the New England coastline are undergoing rapid evolution, particularly with regard to the growth, reproductive, and tolerance traits described by the ERCA hypothesis.

The ERCA hypothesis, and other hypotheses regarding post-establishment evolution, will aid in nonnative plant management by providing information about how nonnative populations interact with and respond to their invaded habitats. By identifying patterns in post-establishment evolution associated with specific habitat characteristics, we will be better able to predict the impact of incipient invasions and will be able to focus management strategies on both current and predicted future distributions of nonnative plant species. Regionally specific invasive species predictive schemes (ISPS, also known as weed risk assessments) quantifying the invasive potential of plant species within a given habitat have been created and implemented in a variety of geographic locations, including New Zealand (Esler et al. 1993), South Africa (Tucker and Richardson 1995), and Hawai'i (Daehler et al. 2004). Such predictive schemes will benefit greatly from the incorporation of evolutionary potential into quantitative assessments and from an enhanced understanding of how the characteristics of invading populations will change over time (Whitney and Gabler 2008). Further examinations of post-establishment evolution that evaluate potential selection pressures in invaded habitats will provide the information required to effectively incorporate evolutionary potential into ISPS and predictive management strategies.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1: Partition of total molecular variability using AMOVA for *L. salicaria*, *S. dulcamara*, and *V. nigrum*, grouping populations by state, and again by state and island/mainland origin.

Species	Source of Variation	Percent variation (grouped by state)	Percent variation (grouped by state and island/mainland origin)
<i>L. salicaria</i>	Among groups	4.6	15.85
	Among populations within groups	48.1	37.55
	Within populations	47.3	46.6
<i>S. dulcamara</i>	Among groups	14.11	27.16
	Among populations within groups	26.19	12.63
	Within populations	59.7	60.21
<i>V. nigrum</i>	Among groups	21.04	20.54
	Among populations within groups	36.78	35.57
	Within populations	42.18	43.89

Figures

Figure 1: Map of seed collection sites for *L. salicaria*, *S. dulcamara*, and *V. nigrum*.

Figure 2: Mean two-year change in total biomass for mainland and island individuals of a) *L. salicaria*, b) *S. dulcamara*, and c) *V. nigrum*. Vertical bars represent standard errors.

a) *L. salicaria*

b) *S. dulcamara*

c) *V. nigrum*

Figure 3: Mean reproductive mass ratio (ReMR) for mainland and island individuals of a) *L. salicaria*, b) *S. dulcamara*, and c) *V. nigrum*. Vertical bars represent standard errors.

a) *L. salicaria*

b) *S. dulcamara*

c) *V. nigrum*

Figure 4: Mean two-year change in biomass for mainland and island individuals grown with simulated herbivory (treatment) or without (control) for a) *L. salicaria*, b) *S. dulcamara*, and c) *V. nigrum*. Vertical bars represent standard errors.

a) *L. salicaria*

b) *S. dulcamara*

c) *V. nigrum*

Figure 5: Mean competitive response of *S. canadensis* individuals competing with mainland and island populations of *L. salicaria*, *S. dulcamara*, and *V. nigrum*, in one of two growth scenarios:

a) a single *S. canadensis* individual grown with a target individual, or b) two *S. canadensis* individuals grown with a target individual. Vertical bars represent standard errors.

a)

b)

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Appendix 1: Neighbor-joining trees for a) *L. salicaria*, b) *S. dulcamara*, and c) *V. nigrum* populations along the New England coast. The number after the town and state name is the individual number. When the town name is preceded by “N” or “S,” these letters represent “North” and “South” respectively. When the individual number is preceded by a letter (A-D), the letter designates one of multiple populations sampled from a single town (but separated by a minimum distance of 1 km). Numbers at nodes represent confidence levels for clades with >49% bootstrap based on 1000 replicate neighbor-joining searches.

a) *L. salicaria*

c) *V. nigrum*

